

Consequences of intraspecific competition for floral resources in heterogeneous landscapes for eusocial bees

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural intensification is widely recognised as a primary driver of pollinator loss, but the success of land-management actions designed to remediate its impact is often mixed. Payments to farmers to increase habitat connectivity or the availability of floral and nesting resources may only result in short-term gains or even unintended consequences. The reasons may lie in changes to interaction networks or competition intensity that remain poorly understood. Models of pollination service typically implicitly assume pollinator population dynamics are regulated by nest-site availability, even though empirical evidence suggests nest-site occupancy is likely at least in part dependent on floral resource availability. To investigate the consequences of competition for floral resources in coarse-grained agricultural landscapes we extended an established model for bees combining optimal foraging and population dynamics, to include new functions for floral resource depletion and realistic colony dynamics. We find that intra-specific competition occurs late in the season forcing bees to forage underutilised sites situated further towards their foraging range limits. A lower rate of energy acquisition ultimately limits the size of the colony peak and delays its timing. Consequently, competition for floral resources can limit population size and distribution while at the same time contributing to a more stable and efficacious pollination service. Although competition was not found to be important in nest-site establishment success, the effect of a hunger gap early in the season on nest-site occupancy indirectly influences competition later in the season leading to complex outcomes.

1. Introduction

Worldwide insect declines (van Klink et al., 2020; Wagner, 2020) have potentially serious consequences for other taxa and ecosystem services (Anon., IPBES, 2018). The primary cause of these declines is loss of farmland heterogeneity at multiple spatial scales (Benton et al., 2003; Clough et al., 2020; Lichtenberg et al., 2017; Seibold et al., 2019; Uhler et al., 2021) that have reduced both the taxonomic and functional diversity underpinning species interactions within fields (Carmona et al., 2020; Uchida and Ushimaru, 2014) and opportunities for wild species to find refuge at the field margins and semi-natural habitats (Benton et al., 2003; Clough et al., 2020; Marshall, 2008). How the resulting more coarse-grained landscapes impact biodiversity, and the delivery and resilience of ecosystem services remains unclear (Tscharnkte et al., 2012) but there is increasing evidence that the effects are mediated by changes to interaction networks and competition intensity, which have yet to be fully understood and modelled (Kaiser-Bunbury et al., 2017;

Thomson and Page, 2020).

Pollinators provide an ideal study system to understand how habitat composition and spatial configuration affects the delivery of ecosystem services in agricultural landscapes (Potts et al., 2003). In accordance with optimal foraging theory (Olsson and Bolin, 2014), empirical studies confirm that bees actively seek out the richest flower patches (Essenberg, 2013; Fragoso et al., 2021), which can be up to several kilometres from the nest site (Kendall et al., 2022) when the pollen and nectar rewards outweigh the associated travel time and energetic costs (Charlton and Houston, 2010). Mathematical models are currently used to show how relative floral attractiveness determines visitation rates to crops (Olsson et al., 2015) and how this ultimately can determine pollinator abundance at larger spatial scales (Häussler et al., 2017), providing an important tool to investigate the consequences of alternative land management scenarios in real landscapes (Gardner et al., 2020, 2021; Image et al., 2022).

A key implicit assumption of these and other pollinator models e.g.

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(Evertaars et al., 2018), is that population abundance is regulated by nest site availability. Population regulation requires density dependence (Hixon et al., 2002) which in these models is not imposed for flower resources, whereas populations are kept within limits by restrictions in nest-site availability. However, little is known about what factors limit nest sites in the field, particularly for ground-nesting bees (Tschanz et al., 2023). The empirical evidence suggests populations are more likely to be regulated by floral resource availability (Goulson et al., 2015; Roulston and Goodell, 2010) and that it is this that ultimately determines nest site distribution (Torre-Noguera et al., 2014) cf. (Higginson, 2017). Behavioural studies have established that pollinators do compete for floral resources, and that depletion of these resources reduces search efficiency and rate of acquisition (Balfour et al., 2015). In response, bees have evolved to make use of olfactory (Eltz, 2006) and even electrical cues (Clarke et al., 2013) to actively avoid flowers that have recently been visited by conspecifics or other species (Goulson et al., 1998; Page and Williams, 2023). Models that do not currently account for the potential depletion by floral resources, and the corresponding behavioural and population responses of pollinators, may therefore fail to predict which landscape management measures are the most cost-effective in promoting pollinator abundance and pollination services (Carlucci et al., 2020; Fry et al., 1991; Langlois et al., 2020). For example, in a recent model developed for honeybees accounting for intra-specific competition revealed that increasing the number of hives next to orchards will not always increase visitation rates to the crop as they are competition will encourage them to forage elsewhere in the landscape (Santibañez et al., 2022).

Competition for floral resources is expected to be greatest during late spring and summer when colony sizes and resource demands peak (Bishop et al., 2024; Wignall, Campbell Harry, et al., 2020), although other 'hunger gaps' can emerge during the season, notably in early spring, when queens first emerge from hibernation, and in June, between subsequent flowering of mass-flowering crops (Timberlake et al., 2019). Supplementation of floral resources during these critical periods can increase bee abundance (Langlois et al., 2020; Malfi et al., 2022; Rundlöf et al., 2014), although simply maintaining continuity of floral resources throughout the season is shown to be more effective (Hemberger et al., 2022; Lowe et al., 2022; J.E. Ogilvie and Forrest, 2017). This could be because it takes time for bees to grow and track changes in resource availability. It has been suggested that a better model representation of the life-cycle of eusocial bees (Crone and Williams, 2016) may help to explain how a temporary super-abundance of resources early in the season can increase colony size (Malfi et al., 2019, 2022; Westphal et al., 2003) yet fail to produce more queens (Crone and Williams, 2016; Westphal et al., 2009), and why these apparent benefits do not always have a measurable impact at a landscape scale (Williams et al., 2012). Mechanistic models with more realistic colony dynamics can help us to better understand the importance of when to supplement resources (Becher et al., 2024) and how this may interact with climate change (Lammers et al., n.d.).

To investigate the consequences of intraspecific competition for floral resources on bumblebee visitation rates and abundance in heterogeneous landscapes we extend the original optimal foraging model by Olsson et al. (2015). We introduce a new floral resource depletion function to account for the effect of visitation rate on resource availability for different types of competition, from exploitation to interference. We also present a new colony dynamics model to simulate the consequences of daily changes in floral resources on colony growth rate and ultimately queen production. We then investigate the behavioural and population consequences of competition for floral resources in both space and time.

2. Methods

2.1. Overview

The optimal foraging model developed by Olsson et al. (2015) for pollinators living in a heterogeneous resource landscape is here extended to include 1) a new floral resource depletion function to account for the effects of competition among pollinators at a given flower patch and 2) a new colony dynamics function to predict changes in colony size and the timing of queen production for a eusocial bee. Temporal and spatial variation in floral resource availability over the season is simulated using a floral phenology function. These imputed values of floral attractiveness are passed to the optimal foraging function at each time step to determine rate of energy acquisition and total visitation rate to a given patch. The returned value of rate of energy acquisition is passed to the colony dynamics function, while the visitation rate is passed to the floral resource depletion function to weight floral resource availability for the next time step. This process is iterated daily to simulate feedback between behaviour and population dynamics in response to a changing resource environment over the season.

2.2. Optimal foraging function

The central-place foraging (CPF) function developed by Olsson et al. (2015) is used here to calculate optimal visitation rates to a given flower patch and rate of energy acquisition. In the optimal foraging model, an individual bee will only travel to a given flower patch if the net energy gained in doing so exceeds the total metabolic and mortality costs incurred while travelling to and from it, plus the costs of otherwise sitting idle in the nest. The CPF function determines the subset of N resource patches that maximises fitness for each nest site based upon their relative floral quality attractiveness and distance from the nest, yielding two important measures: 1) G_i , the total net energy reserves returned to a given nest after accounting for mortality during foraging, i. e. rate of energy acquisition for the colony, and 2) V_j , visitation rate to a given resource patch. These mathematical functions are described in detail in the supplementary methods (S1).

2.3. Floral phenology function

In the CPF model, a flower patch with a high floral attractiveness value is one that increases the *potential* rate of resource acquisition for the visitor, either by being densely covered in flowers thereby increasing the encounter rate, by providing access to flower species with higher nectar and pollen rewards or both (Häussler et al., 2017). To simulate fluctuating resources in both space and time, we imported existing floral attractiveness and nest-site quality maps (Fig. 1) based on land cover data for southern Sweden as part of a previous study (Häussler et al., 2017) and updated to 10 by 10 meter resolution using land cover data from the Swedish National Land Cover data (Anon., Naturvårdsverket, 2019) and Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) data from 2017 to 2021 provided by the Swedish Board of Agriculture. In addition, with the latest associated flowering species lists, estimates of flower cover and expert opinion on floral attractiveness based on the most recent applications of the pollinator model (Gardner et al., 2020, 2021; Image et al., 2022). These maps were used to generate 500×500 matrices representing landscapes 10×10 km in size, with each grid cell representing a 20×20 m area. Corresponding maps for nest-site quality (value 0 to 1) were also available for use (Fig. 1a). These values were used here as probabilities for a binomial distribution to determine presence and absence for each grid cell. Since floral resource maps were previously generated for three distinct time periods reflecting each major life stage: the founding queen, a colony of workers and new queens (Fig. 1b), we interpolate intermediate values (supplementary methods S2) to generate a continuous daily time-series of floral attractiveness, F , for each day, t , and floral patch, j , over a season length of

Fig. 1. Representation of bee resources in space and time. a) nest-site quality (initial nests m^2 averaged over 0.25 max foraging range), b) floral resource quality mapped for three sequential time periods for a given landscape 10×10 km in size (pixels = 20×20 m) and c) phenological change in floral resource value over the season represented for two example pixels calculated using eq. S5.

120 days (Fig. 1c). Maps were available for the county of Scania for years 2017–2021, including in areas considered to be relatively spatially homogeneous and heterogenous. To illustrate model behaviour, we present results from a single coarse-grained (homogeneous) landscape.

2.4. Floral resource depletion function

To model the optimal behavioural response to the depletion of floral resources due to competition we weight the *potential* rate of resource acquisition in each flower patch, $F_{t,j}$ (eq. S5), by the *realised* rate due to competition in the previous timestep. This yields a *perceived* value of the current resource $F'_{t,j}$ based on recent experience:

$$F'_{t,j} = F_{t,j} \left(1 - e^{\frac{-\lambda F_{t,j}}{\phi r L V_{t-1,j}}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where the product of visitation rate, $V_{t,j}$ (eq. S4), the daily replenishment rate of the floral resource, r , the load size of the forager, L , and constant ϕ in the denominator of the exponent represents the minimum resource requirements necessary to support all bees visiting patch, j , and time, t , i. e. $F_{min,t,j} = \phi r L V_{t,j}$. The constant ϕ scales the minimum resource requirements of the patch visitors to the floral resource units derived for the landscape maps.

To account for variation among bee species in their level of search efficiency, we introduce the variable, λ (Fig. 2). When $\lambda = 1$, depleted flowers within a flower patch are encountered at random. This is the default value for when there is exploitative competition. When $\lambda > 1$, depleted flowers are encountered less often than predicted by random, for example because the pollinator can identify and avoid depleted flowers at a distance using scent or visual cues thus saving time and energy. When $\lambda < 1$, this lower-than-expected search efficiency can be interpreted as either depleted flowers being encountered more often than predicted by random chance, or more time and/or energy is expended in gaining a given amount of resource due to interference competition, be it with conspecifics or heterospecifics.

2.5. Colony dynamics function

The number of workers in a bumblebee colony strongly correlates to nest mass, which typically increases exponentially for four to six weeks before reaching a peak and collapsing at the point at which the colony

Fig. 2. Realised floral resource value of a flower patch based on the level of demand and type of competition. A value of $\lambda = 1$ indicates exploitative competition associated with a random encounter rate with depleted flowers; values of $\lambda < 1$, suggest a reduced search efficiency due to interference competition, while values of $\lambda > 1$ suggests the bee can identify already depleted flowers at a distance. Demand here is defined as the minimum resource requirements necessary to support all visiting pollinators ($F_{min,t,j} = \phi r L V_{t,j}$; see text). Parameter values: $r = 1$; $L = 4$.

switches to queen production (Williams et al., 2012). A detailed study of 59 experimental colonies has shown that the rate of colony growth is primarily determined by surrounding flower resource quality and density (Crone and Williams, 2016). We can therefore simulate the population dynamics of workers, W , using the following iterative equations:

$$W_{t+1,i} = S_{juv} W_{t,i} + W_{t,i} \psi G_{t,i} \quad t < t_{switch}, \quad (2)$$

$$W_{t+1,i} = S_{adult} W_{t,i} \quad t \geq t_{switch}, \quad (3)$$

where, S_{juv} and S_{adult} are daily survival rates of juveniles and adults respectively and growth rate is equal to $\psi G_{t,i}$, which is a scaled value of the net energy acquisition rate predicted by the CPF function (eq. S1). The switch point, t_{switch} , occurs once the founding queen begins laying

unfertilised eggs that develop into sexual males. The onset of this event also halts the production of the pheromone that instructs worker bees to rear fertilised eggs as workers so that all eggs laid thereafter this point in time develop into new queens (Cnaani et al., 2000). Since the new emerging males and queens do not make a substantial contribution to colony growth, we assume the production of new queens is dependent only on the resources, $G_{t,i}$, that surviving workers $W_{t > t_{switch}}$ continue to bring back to the nest. Because these resources are then shared among both queens and males, and since queens typically weigh much more than males and workers (e.g. x2.7 and x4.7 in *Bombus terrestris*, respectively) (Krams et al., 2021), the rate of queen production is predicted to be much lower than that of workers for a given amount of pollen collected, e.g. <15 %. Accordingly, we can model new queen production as:

$$Q_{t+1,i} = S_{juv}Q_{t,i} + W_{t,i}\theta\psi G_{t,i} \quad t \geq t_{switch}, \quad (4)$$

where, θ , is the discounted growth rate of queens vs. workers due to the production of a larger body mass and males, i.e. $\theta = p_{q} \frac{M_w}{p_q M_q + (1-p_q)M_m}$, where $0 < \theta < 1$ and M is the mass of workers, queens or males and p_q is the proportion of eggs laid after the switch point destined to become queens vs. males.

It is likely that rate of energy acquisition provides a reliable cue for the switch to sexual reproduction from workers to new queens (Pelletier et al., 2003), if not workers to males (Beekman et al., 1998). A behavioural decision based on energy acquisition could explain the large variance observed for colony size (Crone and Williams, 2016), and the apparent breakdown of the correlation between colony size and queen production in more variable environments (Williams et al., 2012). Furthermore, the observation that the number of queens produced per nest is typically zero-inflated (Rundlöf pers comm.) suggests bumblebees commonly experience levels of resource limitation in the field that result in nest failures, or male bias. To simulate a state-dependent switch to sexual reproduction, colony growth rate needs to be evaluated against a minimum threshold, and it is reasonable to assume that the value of this threshold is equal to or greater than that necessary to maintain a given colony size i.e. $\Delta W_i \leq G_{min}$, where $G_{min} \geq 1 - S_{juv}$. Note that when the scalar ψ is set to the reciprocal of the maximum growth rate, G_{min} represents a proportion of the maximum rate of energy reserves returned to the nest. Nests that experience poor growth rate for a given number of successive days, d_s , are switched to queen production.

In our model, the maximum colony size, W_{max} , is only attained in the most favourable resource environments. In less favourable resource environments, a slower colony growth rate delays time to queen production, but this only results in a smaller colony size if the rate of energy acquisition falls below the threshold rate of G_{min} . While a smaller peak colony size necessarily limits potential queen production, the number of queens produced depends on resource conditions experienced after the switch point, t_{switch} .

2.6. Implementation

The workflow of procedures is given in the supplementary methods S3. The corresponding Matlab R2020b code for the respective functions is given in supplementary methods S4. The list of parameter values used in all functions is given in Table 1.

3. Results

3.1. Colony dynamics

The model reproduces realistic population dynamics for workers and queens over the course of the season, including the observed exponential growth of workers up to a peak before a rapid decline. Colonies with access to greater floral resources grow more quickly to reach a larger colony size. However, the resource-dependent switch to queen

Table 1

Model parameter descriptions and values. Unit notation: eu = energy units, tu = time units.

Sub-model	Parameter	Value	Description	Units	
Optimal foraging	α	0.1	Distance-decay scalar representing the average distance the bee would travel	km	
	v	1	Flight speed	km/tu	
	L	4	Load size the forager may collect	eu	
	c	4	Metabolic rate while foraging	eu/tu	
	μ	0.002	Predation rate while foraging	tu ⁻¹	
	h	0	Metabolic rate multiplier while in the nest (k in the notation of Olsson et al. 2015 or α in Olsson and Bolin, 2014)		
	β	1.1	Metabolic rate multiplier of flying		
	δ	0.1	Predation rate multiplier while sitting in the nest		
	ϵ	1.1	Predation rate multiplier while flying		
	x	0.75	Parameter describing diminishing returns of energy		
	T	1	Length of breeding season (reduced to daily here)	tu	
	τ	variable	Maximum travel time between the nest and a flower patch of a given quality that still yields a net energy gain. Derived value from the optimisation function in Olsson et al. 2015 that accounts for floral patch attractiveness A and the bee's life-history via the composite variable ω .	tu	
	Colony dynamics	W_{max}	600	Maximum number of workers in a colony	
Q_{max}		120	Maximum number of queens emerging from a colony		
S_{juv}		0.95	Juvenile survival rate	tu ⁻¹	
S_{adult}		0.9	Adult survival rate	tu ⁻¹	
ψ		0.00125	Growth rate multiplier. Factor used to equate energy acquired to growth rate of the colony. Range tested: 0.0005–0.002.		
θ		0.15	Rate of queen production relative to workers derived from their relative mass and a given sex ratio using eq. (4) (this paper).		
M_w		66	Mass of a worker bee (<i>B. terrestris</i> taken from Krams et al. 2021)	mg	
M_m		128	Mass of a new male bee (<i>B. terrestris</i> taken from Krams et al. 2021)	mg	
M_q		307	Mass of a new queen bee (<i>B. terrestris</i> taken from Krams et al. 2021)	mg	
t_{switch}		variable	The day a colony switches to queen production.	tu	
Colony dynamics	G_{min}	0.05	Conditional value used to determine t_{switch} . Value is equivalent to a proportional increase in the number of workers with each time step. Assumption. This paper.		
	d_s	3	Number of successive days that $\Delta W_i \leq G_{min}$. Assumption. This paper.	tu	
	Floral resource depletion	F	variable	Floral attractiveness value. Equivalent to A in Olsson et al. 2015. Determined here for each	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Sub-model	Parameter	Value	Description	Units
	λ	1	Search efficiency: 1 = null model for exploitative competition based on random encounters with depleted flowers; \langle 1 = poorer than expected efficiency due to interference competition; \rangle 1 = better than expected efficiency associated with the use of additional cues. Range tested: 0.5 to 2.	
	L	4	Load size the forager may collect (same parameter as above).	eu
	r	1	Replenishment rate of floral resources.	tu ⁻¹
	ϕ	1	Floral resource multiplier. Factor used to equate the minimum energetic requirements necessary to support the total number of bees visiting the flower patch to the 'floral attractiveness value' F . Range tested: 0.001 to 100.	
Floral phenology	s	3	Number of successive floral resource maps available for a given landscape over the season.	
	t_{max}	120	Length of the breeding season.	tu
	b	30	Time interval between successive periods.	tu
	a	0.3	Rate of change between successive periods.	tu

production partly decouples worker and queen dynamics. Faster growing colonies are not always larger if floral resources are limiting earlier in the season and larger colonies do not always produce more queens if floral resources are limiting later in the season (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Colony growth recorded at two alternative nest sites (grey vs black) in the same landscape to illustrate behaviour of the model. Growth rate of workers shown as thin lines and queens by thick lines. Workers of colony 1 (W1) initially had a higher initial growth but a decline in growth rate caused a relatively early switch to queen production limiting the peak size of the colony in comparison to colony 2 (W2). Nevertheless, the late switch to queen production in colony 2 led to fewer queens than colony 1 because resources declined more rapidly late in the season.

3.2. Population dynamics

3.2.1. Colony size

At the population level, competition between neighbouring nest sites tended to reduce colony size and increase variance (Fig. 4). Competition also tended to delay the timing of peak abundance for both workers and queens, although when competition was more intense, a much earlier switch to sexual reproduction was sometimes observed, resulting in very small colony sizes (Fig. 5). These respective responses were exacerbated when the type of competition was interference rather than exploitative, i.e. at when $\lambda < 1$.

3.2.2. Nest site failures

The introduction of the minimum maintenance requirement (G_{min}) for colony growth rate led to a substantial proportion of nest failures, resulting in a zero-inflated distribution of colony sizes. Those sites that succeeded in producing new queens were found to have had access to substantially more floral resources within their maximum foraging

Fig. 4. Consequences of resource depletion for colony size. Frequency distributions of peak colony sizes are shown for a species subject to no intraspecific competition (null model; grey filled area), exploitative competition ($\lambda = 1$; green lines), interference competition ($\lambda = 0.5$; blue lines) and a species capable of optimising search efficiency within a floral patch ($\lambda = 2$; red lines). Note that the Y axis is truncated for zero values for clarity. Data based on one example landscape saturated with an initial number of 144,738 nest sites, of which $>54\%$ failed to produce any workers even in the absence of competition. As the scalar value ϕ increases visiting bees have a greater impact on resource depletion. Parameter values: $\psi = 0.001$; $S_{adult} = 0.90$; $G_{min} = 0.05$; $\theta = 0.15$; $W_{max} = 600$; $Q_{max} = 120$.

Fig. 5. Consequences of resource depletion for the phenology of colonies. Frequency distributions of peak colony sizes are shown for a species subject to no intraspecific competition (null model; grey filled area), exploitative competition ($\lambda = 1$; green lines), interference competition ($\lambda = 0.5$; blue lines) and a species capable of optimising search efficiency within a floral patch ($\lambda = 2$; red lines). Note that the Y axis is truncated for zero values for clarity. Data based on one example landscape saturated with an initial number of 144,738 nest sites, of which $>54\%$ failed to produce any workers even in the absence of competition. As the scalar value ϕ increases visiting bees have a greater impact on resource depletion. Parameter values: $\psi = 0.001$; $S_{adult} = 0.90$; $G_{min} = 0.05$; $\theta = 0.15$; $W_{max} = 600$; $Q_{max} = 120$.

range than those sites that led to nest failures (Fig. 6a). Local floral resources were especially important. Floral resources were almost 6-fold higher for successful nests if quantified within a quarter of the bee's maximum foraging distance, but only 2-fold higher when quantified over the bee's entire foraging range.

Competition had little impact on nest failure rate, since colonies die off long before peaks in abundance due to a lack of resources to meet their minimum energetic requirements (i.e. G_{min}). Even without resource depletion, the model predicts that most nest sites will fail (null model: 53%). However, an analysis of successful colonies revealed some level of conditionality on the growth rate multiplier, ψ . When the value of ψ was small (i.e. when growth rate is low and G_{min} is relatively large) successful nest sites are associated more to floral resource availability in their immediate area, whereas when ψ was large successful nest sites had access to greater floral resource availability towards the limits of their foraging range (Fig. 6b). This interaction suggests intraspecific competition will have greater influence on species with higher growth rates and/or lower minimum resource requirements.

3.2.3. Fitness

Colonies situated in areas with relatively low nest density or high floral resource availability had relatively higher fitness (Fig. 7). When floral resources were comparatively scarce (high value of ϕ), the relative fitness of a colony was more strongly dependent upon nest site density and less dependent upon floral resources. However, the scale at which these respective resources were measured was important. When measured at a more local scale (within one-quarter of the maximum foraging range) relative fitness was not correlated to nest site density, except under the most limiting floral resource conditions. Floral resources in the local vicinity were relatively more important than those situated towards the edge of the foraging range when floral resources were plentiful though the opposite was true when they were scarce. Consequently, there was an interaction between the correlation coefficients between relative fitness and resource availability measured at different spatial scales over the parameter range of the resource multiplier ϕ (Fig. 7).

The number of new queens produced per nest is strongly dependent upon its peak number of workers, although the strength of this relationship depends upon floral resource availability. When floral resource colonies attain about half their maximum size the correlation coefficient between the number of new queens and the peak number of workers is 0.8, but this declines to ca. 0.28 as floral resource availability approaches non-limiting conditions i.e. $\phi = 0.001$ (Fig. 8). While high floral resource availability increases colony growth rate and potential size in the short-term, a higher population abundance is expected to exacerbate competition for floral resources as they decline at the end of the season.

Visualising colony performance over the landscape with and without competition reveals that the most successful colonies are strongly linked to areas of high floral resource availability irrespective of competition. However, competition for floral resources exacerbates differences in relative fitness further restricting the establishment of nests to the cores of these areas (Fig. 9). If bees emerge relatively early in the season (low t_{min} value) when resources are more limiting nests can fail to establish over large areas that they could otherwise develop to be successful in. This has the effect of creating a more fragmented population structure, which in turn influences how competition influences fitness later in the season. Delaying emergence by just 10 days ($t_{min} = 15$) was enough to establish nests over a much wider area, which in turn influenced the outcomes of competition for floral resources later in the season, resulting in a relatively higher visitation rate to more isolated sites (Fig. 9).

3.2.4. Phenology

When growth rate was low (low ψ), the timing of peak colony size was positively correlated to floral resource availability. Conversely, when growth rate was high (high ψ), and colonies approached their maximum size limit, the timing of peak colony size was negatively correlated to floral resource availability (Figure S1). Beyond a threshold value of the growth rate multiplier (ca. $\psi = 0.00125$), an increase in floral resource availability had the effect of advancing rather delaying the switch to queen production (Figure S1). This interaction suggests that a relative shift in the timing of colony peak abundance enables fast and slow growing colonies to potentially coexist, and consequently stabilise visitation rates over time.

3.2.5. Visitation rates

When there is no resource depletion due to competition bees disproportionately visit a subset of relatively small, isolated but florally attractive sites; when there is competition for these limited resources, bees tend to avoid the busiest sites and increase visits to poorly visited areas towards the limits of their foraging range (Fig. 9). To evaluate to what extent this behaviour could impact pollinator deficits we calculated the ratio of floral resources per visitor (Fig. 10). Although floral resource depletion due to competition reduces colony size, the redistribution of bee visits to flower patches in both space and time reduces

Fig. 6. Effect of floral resource available to each nest site categorised by those that ultimately failed or succeeded to produce new queens. Resources are quantified at three different spatial scales, within 25 % (white), 50 % (light grey) or 100 % (dark grey) of the maximum radial foraging distance. Data for successful nests are highlighted in bold. Error bars indicate \pm 1SD. Floral resources are calculated as the sum of the harmonic mean of each patch quantified across the season. Data shown in a) comprise summary data for 144,738 nest sites for the null model scenario with no resource depletion ($\psi = 0.001$), of which 77,679 (>53 %) failed to produce any workers even in the absence of competition. Data shown in b) reveal sensitivity of nest site success to variation in the growth rate multiplier ψ , where a higher value corresponds to a proportionately lower minimum threshold for colony growth rate i.e. a higher starvation resistance. Parameter values: $G_{min} = 0.05$; $S_{adult} = 0.90$; $\theta = 0.15$; $W_{max} = 600$; $Q_{max} = 120$.

variance in visitation rates among sites and can even increase absolute numbers of visits to some areas.

4. Discussion

Competition for floral resources among pollinators is expected to be highest late in the season once colony sizes of eusocial bees peak and floral resources begin to decline (Bishop et al., 2024; Sponsler et al., 2023; Timberlake et al., 2021). Our model demonstrates that bees will initially respond to this density-dependent depletion of floral resources by foraging further away from the nest in accordance with optimal foraging theory (Olsson et al., 2008). This is evident by an increasing dependency of queen reproduction upon floral resources situated towards the limits of the bees' foraging range. As the number of underutilised sites remaining to be exploited decreases, so does the rate of resource acquisition. This in turn lowers colony growth rates, which delays the switch to queen production and reduces colony size, with the exception that colonies with very low growth rates switch to queen production at an earlier date resulting in very small colony sizes. These dynamics between colony growth rate, peak colony size and timing of the switch to reproduction replicate the response of real experimental colonies in the field (Crone and Williams, 2016). The emergence of multiple overlapping cohorts later in the season is likely attributable to the compounding effects over time of otherwise small differences in exponential growth rate between neighbouring colonies. Consequently, intraspecific competition – especially interference competition - has the effect of increasing disparity in relative fitness among nest sites and disproportionately favouring colonies situated at the centre of larger floral patches.

There is growing empirical evidence that the phenology, colony size, queen production and nest site density of wild bees living in agricultural landscapes is strongly influenced by local floral resource availability (Crone and Williams, 2016; Klatt et al., 2020; Riedinger et al., 2015; Timberlake et al., 2021; Wood et al., 2015). While mass flowering crops (Holzschuh et al., 2013; Rundlöf et al., 2014) and agri-environment scheme interventions such as flower-rich field margins (Klatt et al., 2020; Timberlake et al., 2021) can increase population densities in the short-term, maintaining a continuous supply of floral resources is needed to increase abundances year-to-year (Hemberger et al., 2022; Westphal et al., 2009). This is especially important in human-modified landscapes where hunger resource gaps are shown to periodically occur over the season (Timberlake et al., 2019). What is less clear is how competition for limited floral resources during these periods influences

visitation rates and wider community dynamics (J.E. Ogilvie and Forrest, 2017; Pörtner et al., 2021; Sponsler et al., 2023; Thomson and Page, 2020). For instance, landscapes with more mass flowering crops can be beneficial for common species of social bees but detrimental to solitary species (Eeraerts et al., 2021). A key modelling result was that competition increases reliance on more distant foraging sites. While this may have little consequence for relative nest site reproductive success within a species, it could have important implications for species coexistence if one of the competing species has a smaller foraging range (Bolin et al., 2018) or is a poorer competitor for a common resource, i.e. has a higher value of the competition coefficient lambda in our model. One or both mechanisms could explain why managed honeybees, for instance, appear to displace certain species of wild bee (Page and Williams, 2023; Wignall, Broly, et al., 2020, 2020; Wojcik et al., 2018).

A notable quantifiable result from our modelling exercise is that the effects of competition induced here by a change in the floral resource multiplier value were observable over five orders of magnitude. This finding may seem surprising given that colony size varies by only 100-fold but these are population measures calculated at the landscape scale, where each colony also has the potential to respond to a change in resources initially by simply extending their foraging range. In a heterogeneous landscape, colonies have access to different resources within their local foraging range and so their response to resource limitation will vary depending upon their current level of energy acquisition and the possibility to visit underutilised flower patches further out towards the edge of their maximum foraging range. Even so, the impact on colonies is primarily evident as a population effect (frequency), there appears to be relatively little impact on trait distributions, particularly for colony size since failing colonies are often not observed and the surviving colonies are subject to less competition. These factors have important practical implications for the design of field studies that aim to investigate the consequences of competition for floral resources or demonstrate the efficacy of relevant conservation measures, such as flower strips. Firstly, the spatial scale of the study is important since it is necessary to survey floral resources over the maximum foraging range of the species, which are known to vary widely among species and are potentially much larger than realised (Kendall et al., 2022). Secondly, the level of resource competition needs to be evaluated in terms of flower units per pollinator per flower patch (Sponsler et al., 2023) and thirdly the response variables need to be carefully considered, since a change in visitation rate may not result in a change in pollinator abundance, and a change in pollinator abundance may not be strongly correlated to a change in colony size.

Fig. 7. Correlation between colony relative fitness (peak queen number/mean peak queen number) and various proxies of resource availability quantified at two spatial scales: over the entire maximum foraging range (solid lines) or one-quarter of this radial distance (dashed lines). Floral resource availability is calculated on a patch-by-patch basis as the harmonic mean over the entire season. Note that a higher value of the resource multiplier, ϕ , here equates to a lower relative resource availability (see eq. (1)). Colours of lines correspond to search efficiency as in previous figures: low-level due to interference competition (blue; $\lambda = 0.5$), null model of exploitative competition (green; $\lambda = 1$), and high-level efficiency (red; $\lambda = 2$).

The influence of competition on foraging behaviour could have important consequences for interpreting the role of biodiversity on stability of pollination services. Our model shows that in the short-term, individuals are expected to respond to floral resource depletion by preferentially selecting underutilised sites that lie at a greater distance from the nest; in the long-term, the resulting greater variance in growth rates among colonies flattens the abundance peak. Together these behavioural and demographic changes even out visitation rates to flowers in both space and time. Although this behavioural and developmental plasticity may have relatively little impact on where in the landscape colonies have the greatest reproductive success, it is very likely to change predictions of when and where visitation rates are highest, particularly in human-modified landscapes characterised by resource pulses and corresponding ‘hunger gaps’. Importantly, the presence of a single abundant pollinator species has the potential to mask the potential contributions of a more diverse pollinator

Fig. 8. Response of colony size to floral resource abundance and the subsequent correlation between the numbers of workers and new queens produced per nest.

community to the stability of pollination services, be they due to greater trait redundancy (Biggs et al., 2020; Holling, 1973; Isbell et al., 2009; Loreau and de Mazancourt, 2013; Senapathi et al., 2021) or trait complementarity (Blüthgen and Klein, 2011; Hoehn et al., 2008; Staton et al., 2022). Where there is strong asymmetric competition between species, we might also expect observations of pollinator-plant associations in the field to yield weaker trait-function associations (Bartomeus et al., 2018) that will underestimate a species’ potential contribution to ecosystem function (Kremen, 2005; Kremen et al., 2007). For this reason, it is advisable to evaluate species-habitat networks (Bartomeus et al., 2018; Marini et al., 2019) during periods of both low and high pollinator abundance.

Competition among colonies had little to no role in nest site failures, which we find to be almost entirely attributable to a lack of floral resources in the immediate foraging area. Nest survival rates of 47 % that emerged from our model even in the absence of any competition are comparable to field-based estimates in agricultural landscapes e.g. 45 % for *Bombus lapidarius* (Goulson et al., 2010). These low survival rates are expected to give rise to strong correlations between nest site density and the availability of floral resources within the bee’s foraging range, as is shown for *B. pascuorum* in respect to mass flowering crops (Knight et al., 2009). For this reason, species with shorter foraging distances are expected to show greater sensitivity to spatial heterogeneity in floral resource availability, as appears to be the case for *B. hortorum* and *B. lapidarius* vs. *B. pascuorum* and *B. terrestris* in respect to proximity to agri-environmental schemes (Wood et al., 2015). A shortage of floral resources is expected to pose the greatest threat during the establishment phase (Becher et al., 2024), a result that we could confirm here. A delay in emergence date of just ten days was sufficient to allow the establishment of nests over a wide area, helping to connect core areas and provide pollination services to other sites later in the season. The initial dependence of nest establishment on local floral resources is likely to greatly exacerbate the potential fitness costs of any emerging phenological mismatches between flowers and their pollinators under climate change (Gérard et al., 2020). Moreover, while competition for floral resources may not affect the establishment of nest sites, the consequences of an early resource gap on the resulting spatial distribution of colonies in the landscape does influence levels of competition later in the season in ways that impact the delivery of pollination services and very likely the populations of other pollinators via changing species-habitat associations (Cappellari and Marini, 2021; Doublet et al., 2022; Whitehorn et al., 2022).

The overriding importance of floral resources to nest site establishment success also has important consequences for determining environmental factors of nest site quality (Antoine and Forrest, 2021), for while species may show distinct nest site preferences these factors may

Fig. 9. Illustration of the complex consequences of competition on relative nest site fitness and visitation rates for a given emergence date. Differences in fitness and visitation rate due to competition ($\lambda=2$) are calculated relative to the null model without competition. The landscape is the same as that depicted in Fig. 1 for comparison. Note that the most extreme negative values for differences are truncated here to aid visualisation. Parameter values: $G_{min} = 0.05$; $S_{adult} = 0.90$; $\theta = 0.15$; $W_{max} = 600$; $Q_{max} = 120$; $\phi = 1$; $\psi = 0.00125$.

have little influence on nest site density quantified over larger spatial scales. For example, one study on ground nesting bees (Tschanz et al., 2023) showed that nest site density was positively correlated to various soil measures, namely percent bare ground, sand content and relative soil bulk density, when measured at a small spatial scale. Yet, the same study found no overall effect of no-tillage as a conservation management action in agricultural fields. This is perhaps not surprising when you consider that the total number of colonies is relatively small when measured at larger spatial scales, even in natural environments. One study using molecular methods on ground-nesting bees estimated there are between 13 and 88 nests per km² per species (Wood et al., 2015). This contrasts to the average of 101 nests ha⁻¹ (0 to 400; Tschanz et al., 2023) i.e. 10,000 per km² estimated using emergence traps at a much smaller spatial scale, although this figure includes all recorded ground-nesting bee species. Consequently, most queens might be expected to find a suitable nesting site, even if they must aggregate locally at high densities, for example at the field boundary or alongside man-made structures in urban environments (Hennessy et al., 2020; Noël et al., 2024). Ultimately, however, floral resource availability is expected to regulate nest-site density at the spatial scale determined by the species foraging range.

Introducing competition for floral resources into the central place foraging (CPF) model has potentially important consequences for our understanding of bee dynamics in human-modified landscapes and potential limitations of current modelling approaches to inform land-management and agricultural policy. Earlier versions of a similar

pollinator model (Häussler et al., 2017), for example, have been used to assess the potential value of agri-environmental scheme participation (Image et al., 2022) and field boundary features (Gardner et al., 2021) in promoting pollinator abundance and crop pollination services in England. The CPF model (Olsson et al. 2015) has shown to be an improvement on simpler pollinator model because it can account for a trade-off between floral attractiveness and travel time to the patch (Nicholson et al., 2019). While accounting for optimal foraging behaviour had limited consequence for estimating population size at the landscape scale, the CPF model was better at predicting visitation rates to flower patches, particularly in complex landscapes. Similarly, in this study, we demonstrate that while competition may have little influence on where in the landscape colonies have the greatest fitness, it does strongly influence when and where in the landscape visitation rates are highest. However, by combining the effects of competition for floral resources later in the season with the need for a minimum threshold of floral resources to establish a nest demonstrates how complex interactions can arise. The partial decoupling of nest site fitness and visitation rates to flower patches within the foraging range may help to explain why previous efforts to calibrate these models using estimates of bee abundance have yielded mixed results (Baey et al., 2023; Gardner et al., 2020).

5. Conclusions

Here we demonstrate how intraspecific competition for floral

Fig. 10. Consequences of resource depletion and competition on peak visitation rates across floral patches and the potential consequences for efficacy of pollination service. Colours and parameter values as in Fig. 3.

resources strongly influences foraging behaviour and colony dynamics in heterogeneous landscapes. While competition can exacerbate relative differences in fitness among neighbouring colonies, the greatest consequences are evident for visitation rates. As competition increases, pollinators initially make more use of underutilised flower patches sited towards the edge of their foraging range. Reductions in resource acquisition slow colony growth rates, delaying the switch to queen production and reducing colony size. These demographic changes flatten the abundance peak, which together with behavioural changes serve to reduce variance in visitation rates and potentially pollination service in both space and time. These findings have important implications for how we evaluate the potential contributions of biodiversity to stability of pollination services and the efficacy of agri-environmental schemes to conserve pollinator populations and deliver pollination services.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Richard J. Walters: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Ola Olsson:** Methodology, Software, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Peter Olsson:** Methodology, Resources, Software, Writing – review & editing. **Henrik G. Smith:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Supplementary materials

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